

**Effects of social demographic attributes, knowledge about credit cards and
perceived lifestyle outcomes on credit card usage**

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The aim of this paper is to identify and assess the effects of credit card users' demographic and socio-economic characteristics, knowledge about credit cards, perceived lifestyle outcomes of the credit card usage on credit card usage practices. A sample of 177 individuals in Sri Lanka who possess Visa, MasterCard or American Express credit cards responded to the survey. The hypothesised relationships were examined by means of path analysis. The findings offer implications for research and practice.

Key words: attitudes towards credit cards, credit cards, credit card usage practices, knowledge about credit cards.

Introduction

Credit cards serve as a payment device, a source of revolving credit, and a lifestyle-facilitating technology (Bernthal *et al.*, 2005; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001; Lee and Hogarth, 1999; Starvins, 2000). Consumers use credit cards as an easy mode of payment in lieu of cash or cheques for routine purchases as well as for transactions that would otherwise be inconvenient, or perhaps impossible (for example, purchases over the internet) (Durkin, 2000). However, the credit card payment system permits current purchases to be made on the basis of anticipated future income (Hirschman, 1979). Since most people anticipate higher income, credit card purchases by an individual may exceed cash purchases in purchasing expenditure as well as in item volume (Hirschman, 1979 p. 60). Consumers also use credit cards as a mode of financing and elect to pay interest charges on the unpaid balance (Lee and Kwon, 2002). When consumers use credit cards as a mode of financing, credit cards compete with bank loans and other forms of financing (Hicks, 2005). As a result, credit cards account for a substantial and growing share of consumers' debt through incremental borrowing (Bernthal *et al.*, 2005; Kollman, 2007; Littwin, 2008; Wasberg *et al.*, 1992). The literature identifies the importance of credit cards beyond their use as a tool to bolster purchasing power or a source of revolving credit as a lifestyle-facilitating technology

(Bernthal *et al.*, 2005). For instance, credit cards facilitate those who are in the working and middle classes to achieve a level of participation in the contemporary consumer culture that is different from what would be possible in its absence (Bernthal *et al.*, 2005; Littwin 2008). However, debt and bankruptcy figures tell a compelling story about the importance of credit cards to an economy, where greater dependence on credit cards creates financial difficulties for credit card holders and many carry a monthly un-paid balance (Hicks 2005; Bernthal *et al.*, 2005).

In this regard, financial institutions assess a customer's profitability as a credit customer and tend to refer to those who are in financial difficulties as profitable customers while others would refer to them as financially vulnerable riskier customers (Hallowell, 1996; Littwin, 2008; Stone, 2008). Because of the substantial risks to lenders that financially vulnerable customers will be unable to pay their bills on time, these customers often pay high rates of interest as they are among the industry's most profitable customers. The high interest rates and penalties quickly multiply the original debt, so that a modest number of purchases leave consumers deeply mired in debt (Littwin, 2008). Overall, credit card usage not only affects the macro-economic functioning of supply and demand of money at the aggregate level but also affects the micro-economic functioning of households and families (see Wasberg *et al.*, 1992).

Although a considerable knowledge has been accumulated through research on credit cards, those were mainly centred on the exploration of broad economic issues such as credit card use on the money supply, banking, and retailing (e.g. Berlin and Mester, 2004; Feinberg, 1986; Kim *et al.*, 2005), the development of profiles on credit card users (e.g. Adcock *et al.*, 1977; Hayhoe *et al.*, 2000; Hirschman, 1979; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001; Slocum and Matthews, 1970) and non-users (e.g. Kaynak and Harcar, 2001), and consumers' awareness of credit regulation (e.g. Cunningham and Cunningham, 1976; Littwin, 2008). On the one hand, a majority of these studies have been confined to the Western societies (e.g. Bernthal *et al.*, 2005; Slocum and Matthews, 1970; Littwin, 2008) although few empirical research studies have been conducted in the other parts of the world

(e.g. Barker and Sekerkaya, 1992; Goyal, 2006; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001). On the other hand, scholars highlight the need to go beyond correlational studies explaining cause and effect relationships between credit card possession and spending (e.g. Feinberg, 1986). However, empirical investigations on the ownership and usage practices of credit cards are rare to be found and appear to present unique and important challenges for research. Therefore, this study undertaken in Sri Lanka is unique in its approach as no known previous research has attempted to analyse the areas addressed in this study. The specific objective of this paper is to present and discuss the findings of the study conducted in Sri Lanka to identify and assess the effects of credit card users' demographic and socio-economic characteristics, knowledge about credit cards, the perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage on credit card usage practices. The survey research methodology was used in the study and the hypothesised relationships were examined by means of path analysis. It is expected that the findings presented in this paper will be able to provide practitioners with valuable information about credit card users in an Asian developing country, where credit card business is a lucrative banking service today. In addition, the findings of this exploratory study will be able to establish baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

In order to provide the context for the research, in the next section, relevant literature is briefly reviewed. This is followed by the discussion of the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Theoretical background

Knowledge about credit cards

An individual's level of intellectual understanding and comprehension of credit cards and their use, the knowledge of and ability to compare information on credit card costs, and the literacy on personal finance may result in more efficient use of credit cards (d'Astous and

Miquelon, 1991; Berlin and Mester, 2004; Feinberg, 1986; Kim *et al.*, 2005). However, in a time period where credit cards have been aggressively marketed and sold, the widespread use of credit cards raises two concerns. That is, whether consumers fully understand the costs and implications of using credit cards and whether credit cards have encouraged widespread over indebtedness, particularly among those least able to pay (Durkin, 2000, p 623). According to Durkin (2000), these two issues are related because one of the outcomes of lack of individuals' understanding may be over indebtedness. Hence, the lack of awareness of issuers and knowledge about credit card use and debt management are identified as a threat to market competitiveness and consumer interests (d'Astous and Miquelon, 1991). In this regard, the literature emphasises the importance of educating consumers in comparing competitive credit card offerings; utilizing credit cards as a payment device, a source of revolving credit and a lifestyle-facilitating technology; and about fees, interest rates, and the methods of calculating interest charges (Bernthal *et al.*, 2005; d'Astous and Miquelon, 1991; Kim *et al.*, 2005). Overall, the above reviewed literature suggests that individuals' knowledge about credit cards influence their credit card ownership and usage practices.

Perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage

Consumer perceptions towards lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage influence their credit card usage practices (Lee and Kwon, 2002; Littwin, 2008; Wasberg *et al.*, 1992). Although debt, at one time, was regarded as something to be avoided, past studies provide evidence that consumers, in general, have positive attitudes towards credit cards and credit card debt (Hayhoe *et al.*, 2000; Warwick and Mansfield, 2000; Xiao *et al.*, 1995). The literature also suggests that consumers who have more positive attitude towards credit are more likely to use credit cards for purchases than those who have more negative attitudes (Wasberg *et al.*, 1992).

Previous studies provide evidence that some individuals use credit cards as a symbol to access mainstream society (e.g. Littwin, 2008). For instance, according to Littwin (2008)

for many women credit cards have become a symbol of access to mainstream American society. Further, one of the best predictors of consumer purchase behaviour is the benefits sought from a product or a service (Hirschman, 1979; Lee and Kwon, 2002). The popularity of credit cards as a payment medium is due to the recognition credit cards received as a relatively painless way of spending with the limited liability of lost/stolen cards and due to additional enhancements attached to the use of credit cards, for instance, in terms of purchasing expenditure (Hirschman, 1979; Lee and Kwon, 2002; Whitesell, 1992). Hence, there is a facilitative effect of credit cards, where consumers spend more with credit cards (Slocum and Matthews, 1970). However, there are variations in consumer attitudes towards the usage of credit cards for different products and services, such as using credit for education and for luxury items (see Lee and Kwon, 2002). Furthermore, Hirschman (1979) reports that the credit card possession and use are positively related to the anticipation and actualization of future use. In this regard, Feinberg (1986) argues that the explanation of this relationship is, in general, economic and rational. However, Feinberg (1986) concludes that the cause and effect relationship between the usage of credit cards and credit card spending has yet to be adequately explored.

Based on the perceptions of credit card users towards credit card usage, some researchers classify credit card users into two groups as active and inactive, where active card holders show more positive attitudes towards card usage (e.g. Danes and Hira, 1990; Etzel and Jones, 1978; Roberts and Jones, 2001; Slocum and Matthews, 1970) while inactive users do not feel credit cards as a convenient method of payment when making small purchases (e.g. Etzel and Jones, 1978). As attitudes towards credit card usage is one of the most important factors differentiating active credit card holders from inactive holders (e.g. Danes and Hira, 1990; Roberts and Jones, 2001; Slocum and Matthews 1970), credit card issuing institutions should be aware of the attitudes of credit card holders towards credit cards and how their attitudes influence credit card usage practices (Kaynak and Harcar, 2001).

Credit card usage practices

The literature identifies credit card usage practices as reasons for owning credit cards, the number of credit cards owned, the type of credit card purchases, the place of purchase, the frequency of usage, payment practices, the credit history of consumers, and the amount of monthly expenses through credit cards (e.g. Danes and Hira, 1990; Feinberg, 1986; Hayhoe *et al.*, 2000; Hirschman, 1979; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001).

With regard to reasons for owning credit cards, these are used as a payment medium due to the unavailability of cash where credit cards serve as an open-ended, easily available credit source to purchase goods or services (Durkin, 2000; Wasberg *et al.*, 1992). Credit cards also offer convenience of not carrying cash- a large amount of cash- or convenience when making purchases by telephone (Durkin, 2000; Lee and Kwon, 2002; Wasberg *et al.*, 1992). Further, the payment by credit cards provides ease in maintaining records of purchases (Wasberg *et al.*, 1992). Furthermore, consumers may feel that savings may result in when buying the item now and paying later.

Much of the literature on credit card usage practices examined the type of credit card purchases (e.g. Hayhoe *et al.*, 2000; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001; Lindley *et al.*, 1989), the place of purchase (e.g. Hayhoe *et al.*, 2000; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001), credit history (Kim *et al.*, 2005) and the amount of monthly expenses through credit cards (Kaynak and Harcar, 2001). For instance, past studies provide evidence that females use credit cards more for household goods, clothing and personal belongings (Lindley *et al.*, 1989; Hayhoe *et al.*, 2000; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001) while males use cards more for electronics, entertainment, travel and food away from home (Kaynak *et al.*, 1995; Hayhoe *et al.*, 2000; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001).

With regard to payment practices, the literature provides evidence that convenience users, who use credit cards as an easy mode of payment, typically pay their balance in full upon receiving the account statement (Lee and Hogarth, 1999) while revolvers, who use the card principally as a mode of financing, elect to pay interest charges on the unpaid balance (Lee and Kwon, 2002).

Demographic and socio-economic characteristics of credit card users

The literature identifies demographic and socio-economic characteristics of credit card users' as significant predictors of consumer attitudes and practices in the use of credit cards (e.g. Hirschman, 1979; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001; Lee and Kwon, 2002). These characteristics are suggested to be a reflection of credit card issuers' policies and limits, where credit card issuers penetrate different demographic and socio-economic markets by relaxing eligibility standards and requirements during saturated market conditions (Xiao *et al.*, 1995). Some of the demographic and socio-economic characteristics found to be significant in describing consumer credit card ownership and usage practices are age, sex, marital status, the level of education, the number of dependents in the family, monthly income, the length of credit card ownership, and debt ceiling (e.g. Hirschman, 1979; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001; Lee and Kwon, 2002; Slocum and Matthews, 1970).

Although age is identified as a determinant of credit card ownership and use research findings have produced mixed and generally inconclusive results. For instance, some researchers showed that credit cards are used more extensively by middle-aged persons (e.g. Barker and Sekerkaya, 1992; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001) while some others showed a negative impact of age on credit card usage (e.g. Adcock *et al.*, 1977; Wasberg *et al.*, 1992). With regard to the influence of sex on the type of credit card purchases, females are found to use credit cards more for household goods, clothing and personal belongings than males (e.g. Lindley *et al.*, 1989; Hayhoe *et al.*, 2000; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001).

Marital status and the number of members in the family are also found to influence credit card ownership and use, where married persons are found to possess more credit cards than any other civil status group (e.g. Delener and Katzenstein, 1994) and two-person households are found to have more credit cards than single-person households (e.g. Kinsey, 1981). The literature also provides evidence for a positive relationship between the level of education and credit card usage, where respondents with a high level of education tend to own and use credit cards more often (e.g. Lee and Kwon, 2002). Income is also identified as

having a strong positive relationship with credit card usage, where a higher-income groups are found to possess a large number of credit cards and spend more on different product categories than a lower-income groups (e.g. Barker and Sekerkaya, 1992; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001).

Past studies also identify the number of years an individual is using a credit card or the length of credit card ownership as an age or time-related variable (e.g. Kaynak and Harcar, 2001). According to Kaynak and Harcar (2001), credit card users have more positive attitudes towards credit card usage with the length of credit card ownership. Some other researchers found a positive relationship between the amount of credit card debt and household net income (e.g. Wasberg *et al.*, 1992).

Proposition

As empirical literature on credit card ownership and usage practices are rare, it is difficult to find an established framework or much information on the dimensions explored in this study. For this Sri Lankan study, therefore, it is proposed that interrelationships exist between credit card users' demographic and socio-economic characteristics, knowledge about credit cards, the perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage, and credit card usage practices (refer to Figure 1). Therefore, it is proposed:

Proposition: There would be significant relationships exist between credit card users' demographic and socio-economic characteristics, knowledge about credit cards, the perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage, and credit card usage practices.

In the study, eight demographic and socio-economic characteristics of credit card users were explored, namely, age, sex, marital status, the level of education, the number of dependents in the family, monthly income, the length of credit card ownership, and debt ceiling. Past research identified credit card usage practices to encompass several aspects such as reasons for owning credit cards, the number of credit cards owns, the type of credit

card purchases, the place of purchase, the frequency of usage, and payment practices (e.g. Danes and Hira, 1990; Feinberg, 1986; Hirschman, 1979). However, in the current study the term “credit card usage practices” is used to include reasons for owning credit cards. Knowledge about credit cards is referred to as an individual’s level of understanding and comprehension of credit cards and their use, the knowledge of and ability to compare information on credit card costs, and literacy on personal finance (refer to Figure 1).

Methodology

Measures

The measures for this study were developed based on the insight gained from the previously reviewed literature that was grounded mainly in the West, and insight gained during the preliminary investigations by the two authors in Sri Lanka. All the constructs were measured on a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Standardised Cronbach’s alpha of the scale was examined and principal-components factor analysis was conducted (see Hair *et al.*, 2006). The standardised estimates and reliability statistics of all measures are provided in Appendix 1

Knowledge about credit cards. The measure consisted of 13 items and had a reliability of .783. As shown in Appendix 1, factor analysis yielded a set of four factors. The total variance explained by these four factors was 57.08%. The variance explained is equal to the sum of squared loadings across variables (see Hair *et al.*, 2006, p. 170). Factor 1 was labelled as ‘Personal financial literacy’ (24.06%), Factor 2 as ‘Complementary/competitive credit card systems’ (16.63%), Factor 3 as ‘Knowledge about credit risk’ (8.17%), and Factor 4 as ‘Alternative forms of credit’ (7.76%).

Perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage. The measure consisted of 13 items and had a reliability of .741. Factor analysis yielded five factors, which explained 64.76% of the variance. Factor 1 was labelled as ‘Indebtedness’ (22.78%), Factor 2 as ‘Access to mainstream society’ (14.15%), Factor 3 as ‘Enhanced spending’ (10.53%), Factor 4 as ‘Facilitated commerce’ (8.95%), and Factor 5 as ‘Financial confidence’ (8.36%).

Credit card usage practices. The measure consisted of 14 items and had a reliability of .791. Factor analysis yielded a set of four factors, which explained 56.55% of the variance. Factor 1 was labelled as 'Transaction convenience' (25.72%), Factor 2 as 'Lifestyle facilitator' (14.57%), Factor 3 as 'Marketing and communication programmes' (8.75%), and Factor 4 as 'Short-term financial support' (8.05%).

The research model shown in Figure 1 is drawn based on the results of the factor analysis.

Take in Figure 1

Sample

The sample of the study is restricted to individuals who possess a credit card issued by a financial institution that allows the card holder to utilize the card for payments and as a source of revolving credit. There are three types of credit cards in circulation in Sri Lanka, namely, Visa, MasterCard and American Express. The anecdotal information gathered on credit card possession in Sri Lanka led to suggest that Visa accounts for about 80% of the credit card market, followed by MasterCard (12%) and American Express (8%). Commercial banks operating in the country issue these credit cards. The study is confined to a convenience sample of 177 individuals employed/self-employed in the Colombo metropolitan area, which is considered as the main commerce and financial hub of the country.

Individuals with one of the three main types of credit cards were taken into account. The individuals were identified through the directories of commercial and financial associations, employees' welfare associations or trade unions, educational programmes offered for employees by educational institutes, and personal networks. A contact person was identified from each association. Each contact person together with one of the authors of this paper randomly selected respondents to be participated in the study. In doing so, attempts were

made to select a cross-section of respondents for the sample to be represented by diverse and geographically dispersed individuals who employed/self-employed in the Colombo metropolitan area. They came from various private, public, and semi-government organizations, from different industries and ranked at different levels within organizations. The participants were briefed about the aims of the study prior to the questionnaire distribution and their responses were anonymous. The demographic and socio-economic characteristics of the respondents are shown in Table 1.

Take in Table 1

When the sample characteristics shown in Table 1 are compared with the labour force statistics of Sri Lanka, of the total 7.5 Million labour force of the country, 65% were male. 13% of the labour force belonged to the age group of 15-24 years, 36% belonged to the age group of 25-39 years, and 51% belonged to the age group of over 40 years. With regard to the educational attainment of the labour force, 16% had General Certificate in Education (Ordinary Level) that equals to 10 years of education, and 16% had General Certificate in Education (Advanced Level) that equals to 13 years of education (Department of Census and Statistics, 2008). The mean household income per month was Sri Lankan Rupees 26,286 (1 \$US= 115 Sri Lankan Rupees), and median household income per month was Sri Lankan Rupees 16,735 (Department of Census and Statistics, 2009).

Methods of data collection and analysis

The questionnaire was originally developed in English and then it was translated into the native language, *Sinhala*, and finally translated back from *Sinhala* to English. The translated questionnaire was piloted with a random sample of 10 credit card users that fitted with the participants of the survey prior to the distribution. Participants of the survey were briefed on

the aims of the study prior to data collection, and their responses were anonymous. A structured questionnaire is used as the research instrument. Questionnaire was administered through face-to-face personal interviews during September and November 2007. All the survey interviews were conducted by the second author of this study, and the survey took approximately 15 minutes to complete.

To analyse the paths shown in Figure 1, structural equation modelling (SEM) with maximum likelihood estimation was performed using AMOS 16. Structural equation modelling technique facilitates the simultaneous estimation of multiple interrelated dependence relationships of the dimensions (see Hair *et al.*, 2006, p. 776). The data provided by the respondents were recoded into two levels (0 and 1), namely, age (35 or less=0, More than 35=1); sex (male=0; female=1); marital status (single=0, married=1); the level of education (less than 13 years of education [low]=0, 13 or more years of education [high]=1); dependents in the family (2 or less=0, More than 2=1); monthly income (Rs.35,000 or less=0, More than Rs.35, 000=1, where 1 \$US= 115 Sri Lankan Rupees); the length of credit card ownership (Less than 5 years=0, 5 years or more=1); and debt ceiling (Rs.50,000 or less=0, More than Rs.50, 000=1).

Results and discussion

Fit measures of Chi-square, GFI, CFI, and RMSEA were used to evaluate the structural model (see Hair *et al.*, 2006, p. 776). The structural model achieved a good level of fit: Chi-square=66.91, $df=40$, $P<.05$; GFI=.96; CFI=.95; and RMSEA=.06 (see Hair *et al.*, 2006). Table 2 summarizes the results. For instance, squared multiple correlation of .474 suggests that 47% of the variation of the transaction convenience is accounted by the length of ownership of credit cards, knowledge about credit risk, complementary/competitive credit card systems, enhanced spending, and financial confidence. Further, squared multiple correlation of .339 suggests that personal financial literacy accounts for 34% of the variation of the indebtedness.

Take in Table 2

To identify the nature of the direct effect of demographic and socio-economic characteristics on knowledge about credit cards, the perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage, and credit card usage practices a series of t-tests were conducted. The results are summarised in Table 3. For instance, with regard to the effect of demographic and socio-economic characteristics on knowledge about credit cards, users with a higher debt ceiling are more literate on personal finance. Married users are more knowledgeable in complementary/competitive credit card systems. Users with a higher level of educational attainment are more knowledgeable in complementary/competitive credit card systems.

Take in Table 2

With regard to the effect of demographic and socio-economic characteristics on perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage, for instance, there is a direct inverse relationship between the length of credit card ownership and enhanced spending, where users who owned credit cards for less than five years perceive credit cards leads to more spending. Males perceive that the use credit cards provides access to mainstream society. Females perceive that the use of credit cards provides them with a higher level of financial confidence (refer to Table 3).

With regard to the effect of demographic and socio-economic characteristics on credit card usage practices, users who owned credit cards for more than five years use credit cards more for short-term financial support and for transaction convenience (refer to Table 3).

With regard to the effect of knowledge about credit cards on perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage, Table 2 shows, for instance, that personal financial literacy is

negatively related to indebtedness. In other words, when users are more literate in personal finance they are less likely to suffer from indebtedness.

With regard to the effect of knowledge about credit cards on credit card usage practices, Table 2 shows, for instance, that when users are more knowledgeable in complementary/competitive credit card systems, they use credit more for transaction convenience. Further, when users are more literate in personal finance, they use credit for short-term financial support.

With regard to the effect of perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage on credit card usage practices, Table 2 shows, for instance, that when users perceive credit cards provide them with access to mainstream society they use credit for short-term financial support. Further, when users perceive a higher level of financial confidence in credit card usage, they use credit more for transaction convenience.

Conclusions and implications

The study sought to enhance the understanding of interrelationships between credit card users' demographic and socio-economic characteristics, knowledge about credit cards, the perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage, and credit card usage practices.

With regard to the effect of credit card users' demographic and socio-economic characteristics, the findings showed that users' demographic and socio-economic characteristics influence knowledge about credit cards, the perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage and credit card usage practices. Specifically, the findings suggest that sex is significantly related to perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage (refer to Table 3), where males perceive that the use of credit cards provide access to mainstream society while females perceive that the use of credit cards provide them with more financial confidence. However, the literature suggests that the influence of sex on credit card ownership and usage practices are mixed. For instance, Adcock et al. (1977) found sex as a significant predictor of credit card ownership and use, where males are more likely to use credit cards than females although Adcock et al. (1977) do not describe the reasons behind

this increased usage. However, some recent studies found that there are no significant differences between males and females in the determination of the benefits sought from credit cards, the ownership of credit cards, the practices of paying interest, making minimum payments, and the feeling that they had on good management of finances (e.g. Kaynak and Harcar, 2001).

The current study found a significant relationship between the level of education and knowledge about complementary/competitive credit card systems. Specifically, users with a higher level of educational attainment are more knowledgeable in complementary/competitive credit card systems, and knowledge about complementary/competitive credit card systems is positively related with the use of credit cards for transaction convenience. The findings of the past studies also suggest positive relationship between the level of education and credit card ownership and the frequency of credit card usage, where respondents with a higher level of education tend to own (e.g. Kaynak and Harcar, 2001) and use (e.g. Barker and Sekerkaya, 1992; Danes and Hira, 1990) credit cards more often.

The findings suggest that the users in the higher income group are more knowledgeable in credit risk. Further, it was found that the knowledge about credit risk and the usage of credit cards for transaction convenience is inversely related. Past studies also suggest that the lower and middle income families tend to use credit cards more than the higher income families (e.g. Danes and Hira, 1990). With regard to the influence of age on credit card ownership and use, the current study has not found age as a significant predictor. However, past studies found age as a significant predictor of credit card ownership and use (e.g. Barker and Sekerkaya, 1993; Danes and Hira, 1990; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001). For instance, Danes and Hira (1990) suggest that the negative impact of age on the usage of credit cards might reflect a cohort effect, where older users may find credit cards less appealing for short-term financing compared to younger users who have grown up using credit cards.

With regard to the predictors of perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage, the findings suggest that personal financial literacy significantly accounts for indebtedness (refer

to Table 2). Sex significantly accounts for financial confidence where females perceive that the use of credit cards provides them with more financial confidence. The length of ownership of credit cards significantly accounts for enhanced spending where users who owned credit cards for less than five years perceive that the use of credit cards leads to more spending (refer to Table 3). Past studies provide evidence that consumers use credit cards as a lifestyle-facilitating technology, where consumers use credit cards to achieve a level of participation in the contemporary consumer culture that is different from what would be possible in its absence (e.g. Bernthal *et al.*, 2005; Littwin 2008). In the current study, debt ceiling and sex significantly accounts for users' perception that credit cards provide them with access to mainstream society. That is, users with a lower debt ceiling perceive that the use of credit cards provides them with more access to mainstream society; males perceive that the use of credit cards provides them with more access to mainstream society (refer to Table 3). When the findings of the current study are compared with previous research, Littwin (2008) found that for many women credit cards have become symbols of access to mainstream American society. This suggests the need of more research to validate the links suggested in this study.

It should be noted that we have not come across previous empirical studies based on quantitative methodology that investigated the specific relationships proposed in this study to make straight forward comparisons. For instance, with regard to the predictors of credit card usage practices, for instance, the findings suggest that personal financial literacy, the length of ownership of credit cards, and access to mainstream society significantly predicts credit card usage for short-term financial support; when users perceive credit card provides them with access to mainstream society they significantly use credit cards as a lifestyle facilitator (refer to Table 2). However, as discussed above, several previous researchers (such as Barker and Sekerkaya, 1992; Danes and Hira, 1990; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001) suggest the importance of the variables that are investigated in this study in understanding credit card users' intentions and behaviour. Therefore, considerable research is necessary to validate the links suggested in this study. The current study represents a step in that direction, and

consequently, makes a small contribution to the analysis of credit card ownership and usage practices.

Overall, the findings of the study could be used by practitioners to understand how consumers' demographic and socio-economic characteristics, knowledge about credit cards, and perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage affect credit card usage practices. This would assist them in determining better approaches to address issues surrounding credit card usage and repayment practices and other irresponsible credit card behaviour. In addition, understanding customer attitudes and credit card ownership and usage practices may assist the development of marketing strategies of credit card issuing institutions.

Limitations and future research

First, we were unable to find previous empirical research that dealt with the variables explored in this study. Therefore, we developed the item-measures for the study. Consequently, the prevalence of survey instrument related problems have to be acknowledged. Second, it should be noted that factor analysis was used as a method of data reduction. To provide readers with a sense of the factors yielded for the three main areas investigated in this study (i.e., users' knowledge about credit cards, perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage, and credit card usage practices), we labelled them. In doing so, we attempted to label them as appropriately as possible to describe the content included in each factor. However, one could propose different labels than what we have proposed. Third, the validity of a measure cannot be truly established on the basis of a single cross-sectional exploratory study. The validation of measures requires the assessment of measurement properties over a variety of samples in similar and different contexts. Hence, future research, in different samples and longitudinal studies, are necessary that compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data. Fourth, the study was confined to a considerably small convenience sample of 177 individuals employed/self employed in Colombo metropolitan area. Although attempts were made to select diverse and geographically dispersed individuals who employed/self-employed in the Colombo

metropolitan area, future research covering a large number of different respondents (e.g. in different regions) are necessary. Last but not least, the current study focused on a limited number of variables. Some other variables, for example, the influence of possessing multiple credit cards by an individual, credit history and credit card debt held by individuals/households have not been explored. Therefore, future studies can incorporate such variables.

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Figure

Figure 1. Proposed research model

Table 1: Demographic and socio-economic characteristics of the respondents (N=177)

	%		%
The length of ownership:		Age (years):	
Less than 5 years	46	16-25	12
5-10 years	37	26-35	44
More than 10 years	17	36-45	34
		46 or above	10
Card type:		Sex:	
Visa	62	Male	77
MasterCard	34	Female	23
American Express	4		
Debt ceiling (Sri Lankan Rupees):		Marital status:	
Less than 25,000	29	Single	24
Less than 50,000	44	Married	76
Less than 100,000	19		
Above 100,000	8	Highest level of education:	
Number of dependents:		G.C.E. (O/L)*	15
None	14	G.C.E. (A/L) [◊]	68
1	13	Graduate/Postgraduate	17
2	24	Monthly income (Sri Lankan Rupees) [†] :	
3	36	Less than 15,000	6
4	13	Less than 25,000	20
		Less than 35,000	30
		Less than 45,000	29
		Less than 55,000	9
		Above 55,000	6

Notes:

* General Certificate in Education (Ordinary Level)

[◊] General Certificate in Education (Advanced Level)

[†] 1 \$US= 115 Sri Lankan Rupees (as at 30th June 2010)

Table 2: Summary of the results - structural model coefficients

Path [‡]	Standardized regression estimate and significance	Squared multiple correlation
Income → Knowledge about credit risk	.61***	.101
Marital status → Complementary/competitive credit card systems	.50**	.122
Education → Complementary/competitive credit card systems	.55**	
Debt ceiling → Personal financial literacy	.82***	.155
Debt ceiling → Access to mainstream society	-.54**	.297
Sex → Access to mainstream society	-.57***	
Knowledge about credit risk → Access to mainstream society	.24***	
Sex → Financial confidence	.60**	.091
Personal financial literacy → Indebtedness	-.52***	.339
Length of ownership → Enhanced spending	-.40*	.090
Length of ownership → Short-term financial support	.47***	.263
Personal financial literacy → Short-term financial support	.29***	
Access to mainstream society → Short-term financial support	.31***	
Access to mainstream society → Lifestyle facilitator	.32***	.114
Access to mainstream society → Marketing/communication programmes	.27***	.259
Length of ownership → Transaction convenience	.54***	.474
Knowledge about credit risk → Transaction convenience	-.18**	
Complementary/competitive credit card systems → Transaction convenience	.13*	
Financial confidence → Transaction convenience	.18**	
Enhanced spending → Transaction convenience	.25***	

Note:

[‡] Non-significant paths ($p > 0.05$) are not shown.

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table 3: Summarised results - direct effects of demographic and socio-economic characteristics

	Effect	t-test	
		t	p-value
<i>Knowledge about credit cards:</i>			
Debt ceiling → Personal financial literacy	Users with a credit limit of more than Rs. 50,000 are more literate in personal finance	4.422	p<0.001
Income → Knowledge about credit risk	Users who earn a monthly income of more than Rs. 35,000 are more knowledgeable in credit risk	3.304	p<0.01
Education → Complementary/competitive credit card systems	Users with a higher level of educational attainment are more knowledgeable in complementary/competitive credit card systems	1.478	p<0.05
Marital status → Complementary/competitive credit card systems	Married users are more knowledgeable in complementary /competitive credit card systems	3.021	p<0.05
<i>Perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage:</i>			
Debt ceiling → Access to mainstream society	Users with a debt ceiling of less than Rs. 50,000 perceive that the use of credit cards provides them with more access to mainstream society	-2.344	p<0.05
Sex → Access to mainstream society	Males perceive that the use of credit cards provides them with more access to mainstream society	-4.972	p<0.001
Sex → Financial confidence	Females perceive that the use of credit cards provides them with more financial confidence	3.441	p<0.01
Length of ownership → Enhanced spending	Users who owned credit cards for less than five years perceive that the use of credit cards leads to more spending.	-1.750	p<0.05
<i>Credit card usage practices:</i>			
Length of ownership → Short-term financial support	Users who owned credit cards for more than five years use credit cards more for short-term financial support	3.282	p<0.01
Length of ownership → Transaction convenience	Users who owned credit cards for more than five years use credit cards more for transaction convenience	1.192	p<0.05

Appendix 1: Summary of results- factor analysis

	Factor loading	Standardised Cronbach's alpha
Knowledge about credit cards:		
<i>F1: Personal financial literacy:</i>		
		.836
I am currently managing my credit card debt well	.749	
Even though I have incurred a credit card debt, I am spending money responsibly	.700	
When I decide to incur more credit card debt, I consider my monthly income	.685	
I am successful in living within my budget	.714	
I know ways to reduce my credit card debt	.717	
I am personally responsible for my credit card debt	.607	
<i>F2: Complementary/ competitive credit card systems:</i>		
		.752
I am aware of the different credit card systems on offer	.635	
I am aware of how fees, interest rates, and methods of calculating interest charges by different card issuers	.758	
I am aware of the costs associated with different credit card issuers	.826	
<i>F3: Knowledge about credit risk:</i>		
		.701
I am aware of the implications of incremental borrowing through credit card without repaying the debt	.579	
I am aware of the implications of getting credit card debt ceiling increased	.578	
I am aware of the implications of borrowing loans/obtaining another credit card to pay my existing credit card debt	.575	
<i>F4: Alternative forms of credit:</i> I am aware of the alternative payment and financing methods	.757	
Perceived lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage:		
<i>F1: Indebtedness:</i>		
		.824
Because of credit card debt I have restricted my social activities	.814	
Credit card debt has a negative impact on the harmony of my domestic life	.671	
Credit card has encouraged me to spend beyond my income	.611	
Credit card has placed me in financial difficulties	.693	
<i>F2: Access to mainstream society:</i>		
		.853
The places where I shop have changed and I now purchase things from better places	.814	
Credit card has enabled me to travel more and meet more people	.679	
Credit card has added a quality to my life	.789	
<i>F3: Enhanced spending:</i>		
		.786
Credit card tempts me to buy things that I do not need	.513	
Credit card has influenced me to spend without carrying monthly balance	.734	
Credit card has encouraged me to spend more and buy more	.729	
<i>F4: Facilitated commerce:</i>		
		.861
Credit card has not influenced my lifestyle to any significant level	.703	
My attitude towards credit cards has changed	.803	
<i>F5: Financial confidence:</i> Credit card has boosted my self confident by enabling me to spend for my needs at any time and any where	.857	
Credit card usage practices:		
<i>F1: Transaction convenience:</i>		
		.794
Safety and security	.763	
Convenience	.756	
Ease of record keeping as bank regularly deliver bill statements at periodic intervals	.599	
Can be used to cover emergency needs	.675	
<i>F2: Lifestyle facilitator:</i>		
		.720
My family members' use of credit cards	.508	
To obtain incentives offered on credit cards such as life insurance, bonus tour packages etc.	.556	
To keep up with colleagues and friends	.696	
The policies of the place of purchase regarding acceptable payment systems	.538	
To purchase items through internet	.712	
Prestige	.592	
<i>F3: Marketing and communication programmes:</i>		
		.695
I was influenced by credit cards promotions	.736	
Advertisements on news paper and TV encouraged me to obtain a credit card	.488	
<i>F4: Short-term financial support:</i>		
		.879
To delay cash outlay	.880	
To help me make ends meet because I often run out of money	.743	